

SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES ON THE OXIDATION PRODUCTS OF SUBSTITUTED THIOCARBAMIDES

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The infrared and the near ultraviolet spectra of the oxidation products of *N*-substituted aromatic thiocarbamides have been studied. Tentatively 2-guanidobenzothiazole, 3-formamidobenzothiazole and 1:2:4-thiadiazole structures have been assigned to the various products.

The oxidation of aromatic thiocarbamides leads to the formation of heterocyclic bases: benzothiazoles or "thiodiazoles" (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 25; *B.H.U.J. Sci. Res.*, 1958-59, 9, 94), depending on the conditions of reaction. Of these the "thiodiazoles" have been assigned a 1:2:4 structure (Hofmann and Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1578; Hector, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 799), but no definite evidence has been put forward to support this point of view. A detailed chemical investigation of the Hegershoff's base, obtained by the oxidation of *NN'*-diphenylthiocarbamide, has been already reported (*loc. cit.*, 1960), and the chemistry of Hector's base, the oxidation product of phenylthiocarbamide, has also been discussed (*loc. cit.*, p. 94). With a view to obtaining further information on their structures, a spectroscopic investigation of these and related compounds has been undertaken. In this connection we have also investigated in detail the infrared and the near ultraviolet spectra of a number of related derivatives of guanidine and benzothiazole (Suresh *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960).

The systems now studied are the following, of which compounds (I) to (VII) are of known constitution and (VIII), (IX) and (X) are of yet undecided structures.

(i). Products obtained by heating *N*-(2-benzothiazolyl)-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide with ammonia (I), $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ (*loc. cit.* p. 94), and aniline (II), $C_{20}H_{16}N_4S$ (Suresh and Joshua, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1960, Part III, p. 152) in presence of lead oxide, where the products should have the structures (A) and (B).

(ii). Products obtained by oxidation of formamidothioureas (also called guanylthioureas) of the following structure:

(III), $C_3H_8N_4S$, obtained by the oxidation of (C) (where $R_1=Me$; $R_2=R_3=H$) which is prepared by the condensation of methyl isothiocyanate and guanidine carbonate. The structure of this thiourea is unequivocal, and by oxidation can lead to a triazole or a thiadiazole of which the latter structure is almost certain (Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2288).

(IV), $C_8H_8N_4S$, obtained by the oxidation of (C) (where $R_1=Ph$; $R_2=R_3=H$) (Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345).

(V), $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$, obtained by the oxidation of (C) (where $R_1=R_3=Ph$; $R_2=H$) (Kurzer, *ibid.*, 1956, 2345; Suresh, *loc. cit.*, p. 94).

(VI), $C_{20}H_{18}N_4S$, obtained by the oxidation of (C) (where $R_1=R_2=R_3=Ph$) (Suresh and Joshua, *loc. cit.*).

The oxidation products (III), (IV), (V), (VI) definitely possess the 1 : 2 : 4-thiadiazole structure (D)

because the formamidothioureas, from which these are formed, are obtained by the condensation of mustard oil and the corresponding guanidine as well as by the action of appropriate amine on the aryl thiuret (Dixit, under publication). The oxidation products cannot be isomeric benzothiazoles because the benzothiazole derivatives corresponding to (V) and (VI) are represented by (I) and (II), and the derivative corresponding to (IV) has also been described (Smith *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 4103). There is no such possibility corresponding to (III).

(iii). Hofmann and Gabriel's thiadiazole (VII), $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S$, obtained by the oxidation of *N*-methyl-*N*-phenylthiocarbamide (*loc. cit.*). This must be represented by structure (E). An isomeric benzothiazole structure is not possible in this case (*loc. cit.*, 1960).

(iv). Hegershoff's base (VIII), $C_{26}H_{20}N_4S$, formed by the oxidation of *NN'*-diphenylthiocarbamide, cannot be represented by a 1 : 2 : 4-thiadiazole structure and may have the structure (G) or (H) (*vide infra*).

(v). Hector's base (IX), $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$, the oxidation product of phenylthiocarbamide of yet undecided structure (*loc. cit.*, p. 94).

(vi). Product (X), $C_{20}H_{16}N_4S$, obtained by the bromine oxidation of an equimolar mixture of phenylthiocarbamide and *NN'*-diphenylthiocarbamide in acetic medium (Sah[†], abudhey and Suresh, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1959, Part III, p. 135), also of undecided structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the compounds were prepared in this laboratory and subjected to necessary purification, analysis and identification before taking the spectra. The infrared spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer recording spectrophotometer, Model-21, and Baird-Atomic spectrophotometer, both with NaCl optics. The samples were prepared as mulls in nujol in the case of solids. Some compounds were run in chloroform solution in liquid cells. The relevant frequencies are tabulated in cm^{-1} and the relative intensities of the bands recorded as follows: s, strong; m, medium; w, weak, and b, broad. The ultraviolet absorption spectra were recorded employing a Cary recording spectrophotometer or a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The wave lengths are given in μ and the intensities in terms of $\log \epsilon$ at the absorption maxima.

The ultraviolet spectra of all the compounds are summarised in Table I and the major frequencies in the infrared spectra of (I), (II), (VIII), (IX) and (X) in Table II and (III) to (VII) in Table III.

TABLE I

Near UV absorption spectra of (I to X).

Compounds.	In 47% ethanol.		Log ϵ	In 0.1N-NaOH.			In 0.1N-HClO ₄ .			
I	2230(2)	2430* 2500* 2840* 2930*	3115(1)	4.45(1)	2230(2)	2430* 2500* 2830* 2930*	3120(1)	2230(1)	2420* 2730(2) 2870(3)	2970(4)
II	2220(2)	2570(4) 2845(3) 2970*	3200(1)	4.29(1)	2560*	2850* 2970**	3250(1)	2580	2820* 3000**	3200
III†	2580			4.39						
IV†	2430(2)	2870(1)		4.16(1) 4.06(2)						
V†	2700	3000**		4.31						
VI†	2740	3150*		4.40						
VII†	2420*	2650		4.37						
VIII	2850	3000*		4.48	2850**	3000		2700	3000*	
IX	2360	2600*		4.26	2360	2600*		2500	2800***	
X	2520	2920*		4.46	2520	2910*		2540	2900**	

N.B. (a) *Shoulder

**Weak shoulder

***Very weak shoulder

(b) The numbers in parentheses refer to the relative intensities of the absorption maxima.

(1) refers to the most intense absorption maximum

†In absolute ethanol.

TABLE II

Infrared spectra of I, II, V, VIII, IX and X.

(I).	(II).	(V).	(VIII).	(IX).	(X).
3415 mw	3367 mw	3378 m	3300 mw	3300 mw	3350 mw
1608 s	1603 s	3184 m	1650 s	1620 s	1638 s
1587 m	1587 m	1608 s	1595 s	1588 s	1580 s
1564 s	1574 s	1582 s			
	1536 s	1543 s	1550 m	1538 s	1540 ms
1492 s	1471 s	1504 m	1500 s	1485 m	1525 m
1440*	1355 s			1470 sh	1490 m
1350*	1351 ms		1330 s	1320 m	1347 s
1309 w	1300 m		1320 s	1300 w	1310 ms
1280 ms	1279 s		1287 w	1276 mw	1277 w
1245	1239 ms	1248 m, 1215 w	1225 m	1244 s	1255 w, 1240 w
1152 s	1189 m, 1149 m	1183 w	1160 w, 1180 w	1163 w	1170 mw
1114 mw	1117 w	1159 w			
				1108 s	
1060 mw	1071 w	1086 w	1080 w	1060 w	1070 ms
1020 mw	1025 m	1031 w	1030 w	1035 m	1030 s
1010 w	1010 w				
970 bs	975 s				
942 m	920 s		915 w	919 w	920 w
932 m	905 m		900 m	900 m	900 m
			890 w	886 ms	890 m
850 w	847 mw	859 w		847 ms	870 ^b m ^b
795 ms	788 mw		798 m	800 m	790 s
727 s	723 ms	736 s	733 s	743 s	725 b ^b
705 mw	710 ms		715 b	720 ms	703 s

*Shoulder

TABLE III

Infrared spectra of 1:2:4-thiadiazole derivatives.

(III).	(IV).	(V).	(VI).	(VII).
3278 s	3412 ms	3378 m	3144 m	..
3154 s	3257 ms 3154 s	3184 m	..	..
1666 s	1652 s 1628 s 1605 s	1608 s	1639 s 1605 s	1600*
1572 s	1570 s	1582 s	1558 s	1587 m
1534 s	1529 s	1543 s	..	1548 r
1499 s	1504 s	1504 m	1499 bs	1488 s
1224 s	1222 s	1248 m 1215 w	1239 w	1221 ms
1170 ms	1179 m	1183 w	1174 *	1170 ms
1117 ms	1101 w 1080 w	1159 w 1086 w	1073 w	1116 m 1076 w
1050 w	1043 ms	..	1054 w	..
1022 m	1031 ms	1031 w	1021 w	1028 w
828 s	836 s	859 w	856 w 795 m	833 w 812 w
738 s	742 s	736 s	742 m	727 ms

* Shoulder

DISCUSSION

The near ultraviolet spectra of (I) and (II) in ethanol solutions are very similar to those of simple 2-substituted benzothiazole derivatives (Suresh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). For comparison, the spectra of (I) and (II) are reproduced in Fig. 1 with the spectrum of 2-anilino-4-thiazole. (II) shows some of the absorption maxima at longer wave lengths than (I). This is probably because of the greater number of phenyl groups in the former compound. Such bathochromic shifts, caused by the increase in the number of phenyl groups, are due to the increased resonance interaction (Robertson and Matson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5250). Both (I) and (II) show the expected variation in their ultraviolet spectra in acid solution (hypsochromic shifts) (Table I, column 3) due to protonation of imido or/and amino groups.

The infrared spectrum of (I) shows only one N—H stretching absorption around 3400 cm^{-1} , which is in agreement with structure (A). Both (I) and (II) exhibit a strong band around 1650 cm^{-1} probably due to the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ vibration interacting with the aromatic vibrations. Simple guanidines also exhibit the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ vibration around 1600 cm^{-1} (Suresh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Further, (I) and (II) exhibit bands in the region characteristic of the benzothiazole nucleus (*loc. cit.*). In addition these show characteristic guanidine vibrations (*loc. cit.*). The infrared spectra completely support the earlier suggestion that the guanidine units are attached in the 2-position to the benzothiazole nucleus in (I) and (II).

FIG. 1

UV absorption spectra of 2-guanidino-benzothiazoles (I and II) and 2-anilinobenzothiazole.

FIG. 2

UV absorption spectra of the oxidation products of aromatic thiocarbamides (VIII, IX and X).

The UV spectra of (III) to (VII) are also summarised in Table I. The bathochromic shifts going from (IV) to (VI) are not uniformly increasing because the aromatic character or the extent of conjugation itself will be different in these systems, as shown by the structures mentioned below for these compounds. The intensity of the band increases, however, with the number of phenyl groups. The spectra of these thiazoles are in a way similar to the spectra of the thiazoles reported by Goerdeler *et al.* (*Chem. Ber.*, 1954, 87, 61).

The frequencies that consistently appear in the infrared spectra of thiazoles are summarised in Table III. The infrared data on these compounds (III through VI) can be interpreted on the basis of the thiazole structures for these compounds.

All these compounds show bands due to N—H stretching in the region 3150-3400 cm^{-1} . The number of N—H stretching bands depends on the types of N—H linkages. In cases like (III), (IV) and (V), there are imine and secondary amine type of N—H linkages. However, in (VI) only

secondary amine N—H type is possible, and rightly so only one band is observed. It is understood that the frequencies observed are rather lower than that expected due to hydrogen bonding in solid state. Because of the two N—H stretching bands observed in (V), the structure (VB) is more likely (*loc. cit.*, 1960). This evidence is, however, not conclusive enough. All these derivatives (III to VI) show bands in the region $1570\text{--}1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$, possibly due to C=N linkages. An exclusive assignment is not possible since most of them have C—C due to phenyl groups. But in (III), which has only a methyl group as a substituent, the bands at 1572 cm^{-1} and 1666 cm^{-1} cannot be due to phenyl groups, but are probably due to the C—N linkages. All the compounds (III to VI) show a number of bands consistently in the finger print region. Of course, compounds with a greater number of phenyl groups show a greater number of extra weak or medium intensity bands in this region. From a survey of the frequencies tabulated in Table III, it is seen that at least a few of the frequencies in the region $710\text{--}1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be characteristic of the thiadiazole heterocycle. Other characteristic frequencies due to phenyl groups, etc. are also seen, but not tabulated. On the whole, the infrared spectra of (III) to (VI) show an overall similarity.

Compound (VII), obtained by the oxidation of *N*-methyl-*N*-phenylthiocarbamide, exhibits the infrared spectrum very similar to the 1 : 2 : 4-thiadiazoles (III to VI). The major frequencies of (VII) are shown in Table III. It is interesting to see that (VII) does not show any N—H stretching vibration as is to be expected if the structure were (E) (*vide supra*).

The ultraviolet spectra of (VIII), (IX), and (X) are markedly different from those of simple benzothiazole derivatives (Fig. 1). All the three derivatives show an absorption maximum and a shoulder at a longer wave length. They exhibit progressively increasing bathochromic shifts in the order: (IX), (X) and (VIII) (the number of phenyl groups increasing in the same order). The spectra of (IX), (X), and (VIII) in ethanol are reproduced in Fig. 2. The intensities of the bands also increase with the number of phenyl groups. The variations of the UV spectra in acid solution are not straightforward in these derivatives (Table I). The results of UV spectra only indicate that (IX), (X), and (VIII) may be very similar. The UV spectra resemble those of 2-imino-2:3-dihydrobenzothiazole derivatives (Edisbury *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1497) and also some of the 1 : 2 : 4-thiadiazole (Goerdeler, *loc. cit.*).

The infrared spectra of these derivatives also show a great similarity to one another. Compound (VIII) (which should have four phenyl groups according to elemental analysis) shows a N—H stretching frequency at 3300 cm^{-1} (even in a solution spectrum). Chemical evidence also indicates an active hydrogen (this *Journal*, 1960, *loc. cit.*). This excludes the ~~1 : 2 : 4-thiadiazole~~ structure (E) for this compound :

So (VIII) may be a more complex derivative of benzothiazole (assuming that this is the only other possibility—chemical evidence apparently indicates the presence of a benzothiazole nucleus) of the type (G) or (H).

A simple structure of the type (H) is, however, difficult to support on the basis of the UV spectrum. Further, (VIII), (IX) and (X) do not show characteristic vibrations of benzothiazole and guanidine as well, as shown by (I) and (II). It is known that the 2:3-dihydrobenzothiazole system shows deviations in the infrared spectra from the simple 2-substituted benzothiazoles (Suresh *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). These observations can be explained by the structure (G) for (VIII). The C—N frequencies interacting with C—C of the phenyl groups in (IX), (X) and (VIII) are seen at 1620, 1638 and 1650 cm^{-1} respectively, showing progressive increase in the frequency with the number of phenyl groups. The frequency variations are possibly due to the bond-order changes caused by the presence of phenyl groups. Also, the complexity of the spectra of (IX), (X), and (VIII) increases in the skeletal region with increase in the number of phenyl groups. The infrared spectrum of (IX) shows some similarity with those of (I) and also (V) [the spectrum of (V) has been recorded in Table II for comparison].

It has been reported that (IX) and its *p*-tolyl analogue, when heated with ammonia in a sealed tube, undergo isomerisation to (V) and its tolyl analogue (Kurzer, *Chem. Ind.*, 1956, 528; Dixit, *loc. cit.*). Such an isomeric change from a compound with the structure of the type (G) (with two phenyl groups less) to (D) is difficult to conceive. With a structure of the type (H) it may, however, possibly isomerise to a thiadiazole structure (akin to V) by snapping of the bond between sulphur and benzene nucleus, followed by rearrangement. Since the isomeric (I) (A) is already known, (IX) is not likely to have a structure analogous to (G) or (H). It is probable that it has a 1:2:4-thiadiazole structure, identical with the one suggested by Dost (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 863) (VA), which can simply isomerise to (VB).

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